

'Neglect-Me-Not' Shelf: Exploring the merger of behavior and movement-based interaction

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Abstract Some studies have investigated aesthetics of interaction and embodied experience combined with product expression, however, the feeling towards everyday objects, such as furniture, have been mostly unexplored by design researchers. In order to better grasp this domain, a case study of movement-based interaction and behavior of furniture is described. After a three-stage process (inspiration, ideation and implementation), an interactive shelf was developed. The 'Neglect-Me-Not' Shelf is a prototype of a shelf which desires human interaction. With the help of dynamic shapes and technology, it reaches richer experiences in users through the combination of behavior and movement-based interaction. As observed through a pilot evaluation, this combination allows the shelf to express feelings, evoking emotions such as surprise and joy in humans.

Keywords *Neglect-me-not shelf, Interactive furniture, Object behavior, Movement-based interaction, Dynamic shapes*

Introduction

"The world is inherently meaningful for us, i.e. we perceive the world in terms of what we can do with it, and by physically interacting with it we access this meaning and express the meaning." (Hummels et al, 2007).

As interactive products become closer in our everyday life, emotional interaction with physical world is strongly emphasized (Lee, 2006). The emphasis on emotional skills in both product and human-computer design is growing as well. On the same demand for new interactions, the market is becoming flooded with products which makes users overwhelmed with choices. An aspect that the market uses nowadays is product attachment which elicits emotion into people, making traditional product design change into designing contexts for experience (Wensveen, 2000). There are several factors to consider while designing aside from emotional interaction, such as function, behavior or brand (Chakrabanti, A. & Gupta, A., 2007). Another aspect to consider next to interaction is the design. The physical shape is critical in its market success – it attracts, communicates and adds value by increasing the value of it (Hsiao, K. A., & Chen, L. L., 2006). In this way emotional responses can incite customers to select a particular product from a row of similar products, and will therefore have a considerable influence on their purchase decisions (Chakrabanti, A. & Gupta, A., 2007). It is clear, that the demand of diversity in design is needed and that human-product attachment is one of possible channels. However, while product attachment is based on emotional interaction, which means evoking people's emotions from products or services, what if these same products or services could express emotions towards people?

The topic of this paper involves everyday objects such as furniture. As from the movement-based interaction definition, most furniture is tangible, so it requires actions such as holding, moving and operating functional parts but as explained by Hummels (Hummels et al, 2007), (cit) *"it is not in the tangibility of the interaction as in its richness"*. Some studies have investigated aesthetics of interaction (Hummels, 2001), embodied experience combined with product expression (Hekkert, 2006). In order to better grasp this domain, a case study of movement-based interaction, through dynamic shapes, and behavior of furniture will be presented. This way, furniture can not only address practical issues but also create a space for playfulness, offering users an enriched experience and new opportunities. The goal of this research is to understand the link between furniture behavior and human emotion, through movement-based interaction. To investigate this unexplored aspect, we selected to probe a living room shelf.

Method

To illustrate the process of the project, we will use three (Designkit.org, 2016) stages: *inspiration, ideation and implementation*.

Inspiration

In this stage it was central to understand and re-create (Simsarian, 2003). The first step was to share understandings from the field and the behavior a person expresses. We used the '*Plutchik Wheel of Emotion*' to map out experienced behaviors to feelings. The wheel of emotion is a model to describe the activation-evaluation-power space of emotion, where each emotional state is defined with an emotional intensity and emotional orientation (Wu et al, 2006). For example, the shelf would punch or

Figure 1. The “Neglect-me-NOT” shelf in a living room setting (left) and the sketch of the scene, picturing the cognition and movement-based interaction (right).

vibrate erratically when experiencing anger. The second step consisted of re-creating a scenario, in which a shelf would already possess a behavior. Each teammate selected a general emotion such as happy, angry, sad, etc. and acted out as a shelf and others had to observe and describe the actual situation. With this method we created a story for each scenario, and with additional research, we created the guidelines for the context we were designing for.

Ideation

In this phase was crucial to ideate shelf on the next level. As mentioned before, shape and interaction play an important role in the product properties itself. However, as mentioned by Hsiao and Chen (Hsiao, K. A., & Chen, L. L., 2006) what brings products to the next level is (cit.) “...the relationship between product shape and the affective responses...”. Since we discovered the behavior in the inspiration phase, in this stage we explored possible dynamic shapes that could enhance movement-based interaction. It all started with desktop and book research of modern furniture design, mood boards, sketching and lastly, fast and dirty prototyping with paper and MDF (medium-density fiberboard) in combination with electronics. The ideation phase ended up with a real-scale model (one and a half meter tall) which was used in the pilot evaluation.

Implementation (pilot evaluation)

The result of the first two stages is the interactive shelf, which is evaluated in the last stage. A preliminary evaluation was held with four participants, in order to evaluate if the combination of behavior and movement-based interaction could evoke an emotion. The shelf was placed in similar set-up as a home living room. Methods such as think aloud and semi-structured interview (Hanington, B., & Martin, B., 2012) were used in order to retrieve information from the participants. Additionally, using the ‘Plutchik Wheel of Emotion’, we asked participants to rate the main emotions faced during the interaction.

The “Neglect-me-NOT” shelf

The “Neglect-me-NOT” shelf (Figure 1) is a prototype of a shelf which wants to have interaction with people.

The shelf feels neglected and sad when people just place or take a book. However, due to its dynamic shapes i.e. separate triangles, it can offer movement when the person is near the shelf (in a range of 3 meters). This range is captured with several ultrasonic and infrared sensors. If the person is neglecting the shelf, the triangles initiate the forward and backwards movement, inviting the person to interact with it. If the sensors detect the interaction (in this case the hands of the person reaching for the shelf), the movement will stop. With this aspects, the shelf wants to express behaviors such as *welcoming* and *approachable* as an invitation to interaction, it wants to be joyful.

Implementation (pilot evaluation)

In the first part of the pilot evaluation, four participants were asked to think aloud while interacting with the shelf (Figure 2), in a set-up living room. From the think aloud method and semi-structured interview, the participants’ shared:

- “It reacts somehow to what I am doing... and it’s kind of suggesting right now << Oh hey you! You ha-ven’t seen my area, look at me>>”. (Participant 1, female, 24 years old, Denmark)
- “I am confused, I don’t know what to do! Should go for the cookie box or the book? Both shelves are moving out very fast”. (Participant 2, female, 24 years old, Denmark)
- “Ooh thank you shelf! I just wanted to take that, this is cool!” (Participant 3, male, 30 years old, Denmark)
- “The shelf is angry with me because I have been ignoring this object for too long?” (Participant 3, male, 30 years old, Denmark)
- “The shelf is reaching out for me. This would be so great for a reminder. You know, I am knitting this sweater for like 3 years now, this would be a great way to remind me to take the sweater to knit since I am forgetting it for too long.” (Participant 4, female, 40 years old, Denmark)

In the second part of the evaluation we asked participants to rate (Table 1) the main emotions they felt according to the Plutchik Wheel of Emotion: joy, trust, fear, surprise, sadness, disgust, anger,

Figure 2. The graph represents the ranking of the 9 emotions, ranked by 4 participants in the implementation (pilot evaluation) phase.

anticipation. Surprise was the most rated emotion by 45%, followed by **Joy**, presenting 22% and lastly, **Anticipation, Interest and Fear** share 11% (Figure 2).

Discussion and conclusion

The shelf was chosen because, from personal observation, we tend to neglect it. Humans tend to minimize the interaction, especially when the only (inter)action is placing and taking objects from it. The shelf resulted as a great example, although this approach could be extended to more objects. The tangible world offers a lot of opportunities to explore, especially by adding behavior and movement-based interaction. We extend the call to the readers to explore different behaviors, shapes, interactions in order to create richer experiences.

At the beginning, when we designed the shelf, our goal was to make the shelf very welcoming, with the triangles going outwards and backwards very slowly, creating a pleasant environment. According to the Plutchik Wheel of Emotion, we were aiming at the emotion Joy (specifically serenity), however the most evoked emotion was Surprise, since participants did not expect the shelves to move towards them. In the interviews some thought that the shelf is angry, others experienced the feeling of invitation or even as reminder.

Our exploratory study consisted of three main phases: (a) Understanding emotions and acting out behaviors of shelves, which resulted in design guidelines. The observation made it clear that the overall emotion the shelves were feeling was anger towards humans that is why the concept of the "Neglect-me-not" shelf was

Table 1. Rank of 9 emotions according to the Plutchik Wheel of Emotion, ranked by 4 participants in the implementation (pilot evaluation) phase.

	Emotion 1	Emotion 2	Emotion 3
Participant 1	Surprise	Joy	-
Participant 2	Surprise	Fear	-
Participant 3	Surprise	Joy	-
Participant 4	Anticipation	Interest	Surprise

realized. Acting as a shelf helped us better grasp the context of the design. Especially, when a teammate would throw a book to the shelf (in this case a person), the shelf would throw the book back with same force. This made us realize that we can impersonate the shelves and give them human behavior, so people could better connect with them. (b) In the ideation phase, many shapes were explored such as linear on a wall set-up, rectangular, circular and free shapes. The triangular followed to be the most appropriate shape that would allow all real-size parts to move, in a living room setting. Moreover, the shape offered a clean movement and authentic furniture aesthetics. Lastly, (c) It is clear that the domain emotion people experience while interacting with the shelf is surprise.

With such project it is expected that bringing furniture to the next level doesn't mean only expressing behavior, but also changing human attitude towards it. As designers we then ask ourselves, what does it mean for the future of furniture?

Our initial assumption proves how the combination of dynamic shape and movement-based interaction add behavior in an everyday object, such as a shelf, and moreover, with such behavior, we can elicit emotion of surprise and joy in people.

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